

The Schrodinger Equation and Two Stochastic Considerations

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In this note, we argue that the Schrodinger equation for one particle represents ensemble averages taken from stochastic momentum values of a single particle at different times, with time being removed. A new time, representing the evolution of the ensemble is then introduced especially for the case in which energy is being added or removed from a system (e.g. $V(x,t)$). The momentum stochastic features arise from the potential (or force) acting in a stochastic manner leading to a distribution of momentum values at x (at different times). If $V(x,t)$, we argue the system adds or removes some average energy at x at t . We suggest that in reality, stochastic amounts of energy are added or removed (as long as the average is obtained). This leads to a second distribution, namely one in energy being established.. Thus, $W(x,t)$ may be expanded in terms of $\exp(ipx)$ for a fixed t or in $\exp(i E_i t)$ for a fixed x . As a result, one may calculate average energy using either $\text{Average}(p^2/2m) + V(x,t)$ or $[\text{Sum over } E_i \exp(i E_i t) E_i] / W(x,t)$. Equating the two stochastic approaches yields the Schrodinger equation.

Stochastic Potential

In classical physics, a particle moves through a region with a potential $V(x)$ such that:

$$-dV(x)/dx = dp/dt \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Newton's second law}$$

Thus, one knows $x(t)$ and higher derivatives. For quantum mechanics, we argue that at any point x , $V(x)$ is an average. At a microscopic level, there are different force hits to a quantum particle with different probability weights. This results in a momentum distribution at each x , with the different momenta occurring at different times. One may calculate average kinetic energy at x and add it to $V(x)$. For a bound system, one would expect:

$$KE_{\text{average}}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Equation ((2)), however, does not allow one to solve for $P(p/x)$ where:

$$KE_{\text{average}}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad a(p) f(p,x)] / [\text{Sum over } p \quad f(p,x) a(p)] \quad ((3))$$

For a more general situation, one may replace $a(p)$ with $a(p,t)$, for example, in the case that one has $V(x,t)$.

Stochastic Force Hits

In order to examine the above scenario, consider a stochastic force component $F(k,x)$ where k is the momentum imparted. From classical physics:

$$F \text{ average } (x) = - dV(x) / dx \quad (dx/dt)$$

So from ((1)) we argue that $-dV/dx$ should give a k momentum factor multiplied by a function of x . A possible solution is:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((4))$$

Next, consider a particle with momentum p at x at t . It has kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ just as in classical physics. (There is actually a distribution of p values if one considers all times.) What is the effect of force on such a particle in a range Δx ? Imagine that one force hit occurs in this range. Then:

$$dp/dt = [dp/ \Delta x] [p+p+k]/2 \quad \text{if } F(k,x) \text{ acts on the particle. We use } [2p+k]/2 \text{ as the average velocity in the range } \Delta x.$$

$$F(k,x) \Delta x = \text{work} = (1/m) a(p,t) f(p,x,t) k [2p+k]/2 = \frac{1}{2}m [(p+k)^2 - p^2] a(p,t) f(p,x) \quad ((5))$$

Here $a(p,t) f(p,x)$ is the weight associated with the momentum p in the distribution taken over time. Thus, two things occur. First, it takes time to calculate the change in average kinetic energy given by $\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m a(p,t) f(p,x)$.

$$\text{Now } F(k,x) \Delta x = \text{work} = V(x_1,t) - V(x_2,t) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, ((5)) appears as:

$$\text{Constant} = E = \text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m a(p,t) f(p,x) + V(x) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, one may obtain the time independent Schrodinger equation. Next, one must consider the case of time (which actually also is related to the time independent case).

Time Dependent Case

Consider, as an example, a potential which changes in time $V(x,t)$. One may expect energy to be added or drained from the system. For a given t , one has a potential which is a function of x and represents an average as there are many momentum hits. There is an average momentum hit given by $-d/dx V(x)$, but in reality many different stochastic momentum hits occur constrained by the correct average. For a fixed x , one has essentially a function of t which should also be considered an average and which may give "hits" of energy.

In other words, $V(x,t)$ may add or remove energy stochastically as long as it adds or removes a certain amount on average. In other words there is an $E(t)$. Thus, one may expand $V(x,t)$ for a fixed x as a Fourier series in $\exp(i E_i t)$ where E_i is one possible energy value. The wavefunction $W(x,t)$ may then be treated in the same manner. It is taken to change in time, so there is no

constant value of energy. Thus, there must be many energies. At a point x , which may have many possible momentum values, one considers the stochastic situation in which there may be many possible energy values as well at different times. This is interesting as the various momentum values at x occur at different times and are needed to establish a particular E value. This E value itself is stochastic and changes and so the cycling single particle momentum values are stochastically changing their cycling frequency.

This is the same as expanding $W(x,t)$ for a fixed x in a Fourier series of $\exp(iE_i t)$ i.e.

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } E_i \quad a(E_i, x) \exp(i E_i t) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Then: } -i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) / W(x,t) = [\text{Sum over } E_i a(E_i,x) \exp(i E_i t)] / W(x,t) = E(t) \quad ((10))$$

where $E(t)$ is the average energy at time t . Then:

$$-i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = E(t,x) W(x,t) \quad ((11))$$

$E(t,x)$, however, may be calculated explicitly using the momentum distribution i.e.

$$E(t,x) = V(x) + [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \exp(ipx) b(p,t)] / W(x,t) \quad ((12))$$

One may replace $[\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \exp(ipx) b(p,t)]$ with $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t)$ yielding the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. This equation is based on two stochastic scenarios. The first is a stochastic distribution of p values at each point x at a given time t . These momentum values cycle to try to create a particular average energy. If $V(x,t)$, then energy is entering or leaving the system and different average E values are stirred up. Thus, there is a stochastic distribution of overall energy values at a point x at time t yielding an average energy $E(t)$ at x . By combining these two stochastic results one obtains the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

It is interesting to note that the first stochastic behaviour occurs for a single particle property namely momentum and not an ensemble average. The second stochastic property, average energy is an ensemble average which nevertheless changes due to $V(x,t)$. Thus, time in the Schrodinger case deals with stochastic changes of an ensemble average value.

Double Stochastic Behaviour

For a bound state, there exists a single energy value at all x because $KE \text{ average } (x) + V(x) = E$. A momentum distribution exists at each x , but there is also cycling among these momentum values. As one moves across x , there are varying resolutions according to $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the idea of different wavelengths. Thus, the interaction of the potential with the single particle momenta is stochastic, but in a controlled manner in that there is the same average E at each x point. If energy is added or removed from the system, different bound state single particle momentum cycling resonance patterns may be stirred up. It takes time, however, to establish an average E , thus it seems that there should be a loss of resolution in time with the different average energy

values being stirred up due to $V(x,t)$. Thus, one has stochastic p at each x and these are participating in different average E at different times, in other words, there is double stochastic behaviour.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the time-dependent Schrodinger equation is based on two stochastic views. First, the potential $V(x,t)$ or even $V(x)$ yields stochastic momentum hits at x at t , yielding a momentum distribution (given by a Fourier expansion in $\exp(ipx)$). This is stochastic behaviour of a non-ensemble average value, but it leads to average ensemble values such as kinetic energy at x etc.

Secondly, $V(x,t)$ implies energy being added or removed so one may consider a stochastic situation in which there is a distribution of energies at x at t yielding an average energy $E(t)$. Thus, an ensemble average, namely energy, becomes stochastic.

This leads to:

$$-i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = E(t,x) W(x,t) \text{ but } E(t,x) W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) + V(x,t) W(x,t)$$

Thus, t does not follow the motion time motion of a single quantum particle, but the Schrodinger equation rather considers a stochastic set of energy values and an average $E(t,x)$ which is related to the time derivative of $W(x,t)$. Thus, various derivatives of the wavefunction $W(x,t)$ are directly related to "average" ensemble values for a quantum particle. The momentum operator $-i \frac{d}{dx}$ is related to an ensemble average of momentum. Used twice, it is related to a ensemble average, namely kinetic energy. $-i \frac{d}{dt}$, however, yields an average energy among different possible ensemble average energies. Thus, time is related to changes in ensemble averages and does not follow a single particle.